

Studies in Angular Furocoumarins. Part II Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of Isopsoralenes

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Ultraviolet absorption spectra of isopsoralene derivatives measured in the region 200-360 m μ , show that substitution of hydrogen at 4-position by a phenyl group, or reduction of furan ring is accompanied by bathochromic shift.

In continuation of our work¹ on substitution effect on UV spectra of furocoumarins, we have now studied furo-2'-methyl-5', 4': 7, 8-coumarins substituted at 3, 4-positions, and compared their UV spectra with those of natural isopsoralene.

Furo-2'-methyl-5', 4': 7, 8-coumarins IV have been prepared by the method described in Part-I¹. In this connection, it was surprising to note that compounds I(f), (g) and (i) failed to undergo dehydrogenation to yield the corresponding isopsoralene derivatives IV(f), (g) and (i). These compounds were prepared according to the method of Kaufman² which consists in acetylation of 8-allyl-7-hydroxycoumarins, bromination at the allylic double bond and subsequent cyclization of the resulting 7-acetoxy-8-(2', 3'-dibromopropyl) coumarins (III) with ethanolic caustic soda solution.

- I (a) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$
 (b) $R_1 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = \text{H}$
 (c) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{OH}$
 (d) $R_1 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = \text{ethyl}$

- II (e) $R_1 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = \text{isopropyl}$
 (f) $R_1 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = \text{n-butyl}$
 III (g) $R_1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, R_2 = \text{H}$
 IV (h) $R_1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, R_2 = \text{CH}_3$
 (i) $R_1, R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$

EXPERIMENTAL

Derivatives of furo-5', 4': 7, 8-coumarin (Isopsoralene). These were prepared either by dehydrogenation of furo-2', 3'-dihydro-2'-methyl-3,4-substituted coumarins with Pd/C.¹ or as described by Kaufman². Compounds prepared by either method are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Derivatives of Furo-2'-methyl-5',4': 7,8-coumarin

Compd. IV	M.P. °C	Crystn. Solvent	Yield%		Formula	Analysis%			
			Method Ia	Method II ^b		Carbon		Hydrogen	
					required	Found	required	Found	
(c)	193-194	Methanol	71		C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃	73.67	74.01	5.30	5.42
(d)	149-150	Methanol	84		C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃	74.36	74.74	5.83	5.81
(e)	135-136	Methanol	40		C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃	74.98	75.30	6.29	6.52
(f)	100-101	Methanol		90	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₃	75.53	75.27	6.71	7.05
(g)	157-158	Methanol		76	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₃	78.25	78.42	4.38	4.61
(i)	185-186	Methanol		92	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃	74.99	74.70	5.03	5.23

a. Based on weight of dihydro compound taken.

b. Based on weight of dibromo compound taken.

TABLE II

3,4-Alkyl and-aryl derivatives of 7-acetoxy-8-allyl coumarin

Compd. II.	M.P. °C.	Crystn. Solvent	Yield %	Formula	Analysis %			
					Carbon		Hydrogen	
					required	Found	required	Found
(f)	110-111	Methanol	74	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₄	72.59	72.29	7.05	7.18
(g)	77-78	Methanol	79	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄	74.99	74.92	5.03	5.30
(i)	123-124	Methanol	83	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄	71.82	71.98	5.67	5.64

TABLE III

3,4-Alkyl and-aryl derivatives of 7-acetoxy-8-(2',3'-dibromopropyl) coumarin

Compd. III.	M.P. °C	Crystn. Solvent	Yield%	Formula	Analysis%			
					Carbon		Hydrogen	
					required	Found	required	Found
(f)	129-130	Methanol	92	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ Br ₂ O ₄	48.10	48.20	4.68	4.90
(g)	134-135	Methanol	80	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ Br ₂ O ₄	50.00	50.28	3.33	3.24
(i)	123-124	Methanol	68.5	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ Br ₂ O ₄	45.85	45.65	3.60	3.67

2. Part I.

3. Kaufman, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 117.